

Medium Effects on Alkaline Hydrolysis of *N*-Phenylbenzohydroxamic Acid

KALLOL K GHOSH* and SHARMISTHA GHOSH

School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur-492 010

Manuscript received 30 April 1993, revised 28 July 1993, accepted 12 October 1993

Kinetic studies of alkaline hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid have been investigated in aqueous dioxane, dimethyl sulphoxide, dimethyl formamide, acetone, acetonitrile, methanol and ethanol mixtures of varying compositions (0–80%, v/v) at different temperatures (55–75°). The rate constant in all cases increases with increasing percentage of the solvent, which is attributed to solvation of the transition state, solute-solvent interactions and dielectric behaviour of the medium. The activation parameters have been evaluated and discussed in terms of solvation effect.

Despite extensive studies, the solvent effect on homogenous chemical reaction is still incompletely understood. Recent years have, therefore, witnessed increasing attempts on medium effects in mixed aqueous solvents. These mixed aqueous solvents are of current interest because of their pronounced effect on rates of reactions. It has been known that a change of medium can considerably influence the reactivity of chemical reactions. Many works have been published on the rationalisation of kinetic solvent effects on various reactions^{1,2}. The studies of the solvent effects on the hydrolysis of esters and amides have been carried out by a number of workers^{3,4}. However, no kinetic studies have been previously attempted on the solvent effect on the alkaline hydrolysis of hydroxamic acid. In the present article, therefore, an attempt has been made to study the effect of various diverse solvents on the alkaline hydrolysis of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid, (PBHA). Recently⁵ on the basis of chemometric empirical scale of parameters, the solvents have been classified as little polar basic, polar aprotic, polar protic, etc. Therefore, in the present study, we have chosen dioxane, acetone (little polar basic), dimethyl sulphoxide, acetonitrile, dimethyl formamide (polar aprotic), methanol, ethanol (polar-protic) solvents.

Results and Discussion

The alkaline hydrolysis of PBHA is of the first order in both the substrate and hydroxide anion. The kinetics were studied by varying the percentage cosolvent from 10 to 80% (v/v) in binary aqueous mixture at 55–75°. The concentration of catalysing base, NaOH and PBHA was 1 *M* and around 6.0×10^{-3} *M* respectively. The mechanism of base catalysed hydrolysis of PBHA is published elsewhere⁶.

The kinetic findings of this work are presented in Table 1 and represented graphically in Fig. 1. Results show that at all the solvents the observed rate constants increase with increasing proportion of solvents at all the temperatures. The influence of solvent on the rates of many organic reactions has received much attention. However, no simple theory appears adequate to explain the effects observed. How a particular solvent will effect the rate is difficult to explain and what is experimentally observed is the net effect. It is necessary to consider the solvent structure, properties, solute-solvent interaction, solvation of transition state and dielectric constant.

Dioxane is typical dipolar aprotic solvent with lowest dielectric constant ($D = 2.1$) of all the

TABLE-1 PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR BASE CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF PBHA IN DIFFERENT BINARY AQUEOUS MIXTURES

Solvent % (v/v)	$k_{\psi} \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$																				
	Dioxane			DMSO			MeOH			EtOH			Me ₂ CO			DMF			MeCN		
	55 ⁰	65 ⁰	75 ⁰	55 ⁰	65 ⁰	75 ⁰	55 ⁰	65 ⁰	75 ⁰	55 ⁰	65 ⁰	75 ⁰	55 ⁰	65 ⁰	75 ⁰	55 ⁰	65 ⁰	75 ⁰	55 ⁰	65 ⁰	75 ⁰
0	-	0.70	-	-	0.70	-	-	0.70	-	-	0.70	-	-	0.70	-	-	0.70	-	-	0.70	-
10	0.43	1.09	2.99	0.32	1.06	3.31	0.47	1.26	2.75	0.34	0.91	2.06	0.37	0.85	2.06	0.47	1.55	4.33	0.26	0.88	2.52
20	0.51	1.57	3.86	-	-	3.73	-	1.91	-	-	1.87	-	0.80	1.23	4.19	-	1.64	-	-	0.96	-
30	0.76	2.24	5.12	0.58	1.58	4.46	0.78	2.60	6.11	0.94	2.72	6.42	-	2.03	-	1.27	3.23	9.71	0.44	1.25	3.63
40	1.12	3.12	6.87	0.78	2.58	5.09	-	2.76	-	-	3.21	-	-	3.5	-	-	4.55	-	-	2.08	-
50	1.99	4.46	11.8	-	-	9.21	1.02	3.20	7.63	1.24	3.61	9.85	1.96	4.99	13.0	2.08	5.76	16.5	1.53	4.24	11.4
60	3.02	6.31	15.9	-	-	18.6	-	3.24	-	-	5.21	-	2.41	5.93	13.5	-	6.98	-	-	7.52	-
70	4.28	8.78	19.9	8.83	12.0	24.6	-	3.56	-	-	6.01	-	3.25	7.78	19.3	-	-	-	4.19	11.1	27.6
80	5.50	15.3	20.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.46	9.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

organic cosolvents, having nearly zero dipole moment. It is evident from Table 1 that the observed first order rate constant gradually increases with increasing dioxane content at all the three temperatures. Qualitative solvent-effect theory⁷ predicts that for a reaction between a neutral substrate and an anion involving charge dispersion in the transition state, decreasing the polarity of the medium will cause a rate increase. The main factors, which cause change in the rate with increasing dioxane content are the decreasing availability of the protic solvating species and the decreasing dielectric constant of the medium. When dioxane is added to an aqueous solution, dioxane-water hydrogen-bonded complexes are formed⁸. However, dioxane is a hydrogen-bond acceptor of strength comparable only to water. Dioxane-water was also identified as a TA mixture⁹. A TA solvent exerts a water 'structure-forming' action. Thus 'free-water' is markedly depleted by replacement of water by dioxane in dioxane-water medium.

Like dioxane, the rate constant in all three temperatures increases with increasing DMSO content. Hydroxide ion is a stronger base in DMSO than in water¹⁰. Hydroxide in DMSO mixture form powerful kinetic and thermodynamic base systems², which have been used for proton abstraction and elimination reactions. In DMSO, rate enhancement is due mainly to favourable solvation of transition states by the mixture. Protic solvation is more important for transition state which

have a localised charge structure than those in which the charge is delocalised. Thus reaction which involves attack by hydroxide ion at a carbonyl group requires more protic solvation for the 'alkoxide' like transition state than reaction which proceeds by abstraction of proton by hydroxide anion from a carbon acid, having a delocalised 'enolate' like transition state.

DMF is a polar aprotic solvent like DMSO. DMF shows increasingly positive trend with the increasing percentage of the solvent, as is expected from the destabilising effect of the aproticity of DMF, besides the Born-type electrostatic effect. DMF forms stable hydrates¹¹ imparting more proticity to the H-bonded intercomponent complex. Thus the complex formed is likely to be more effective for solvation of protophilic anion like OH⁻ which can undergo 'localised hydrolysis' type interaction¹² than that for non-protophilic anion.

According to Hughes and Ingold⁷ theory the rate of the reaction between an ion and a dipolar molecule must increase as the polarity of the solvent decreases, due to the dispersal of the charge on the activated complex. Aqueous acetone medium shows perfect agreement with such theory as shown in Table 1. The results show the rate enhancement of the hydrolysis reaction of PBHA with the increasing percentage of acetone medium.

The present behaviour of rate enhancement upon the addition of acetonitrile can be explained simply in terms of the repulsion between the negative dipolar end of MeCN and the negative charge of the anionic solute present in the system. It is well known that the negative end of the dipole in MeCN is exposed, whereas the positive one is buried in the middle of the molecule. Accordingly, anionic nucleophiles would be strongly destabilised upon the addition of MeCN in water and significant rate enhancements is observed in the present reaction. There is no doubt that the anionic nucleophile used in the present study would become more destabilised as the concentration of MeCN is increased in the medium. The change of the solvent structure is considered to be responsible for the present rate behaviour. Recently systematic studies have been initiated by Um *et al.*¹³ for the reaction of esters with anionic nucleophiles in various solvent systems.

The peculiar structural features of aqueous alcohol solutions produce remarkable effects on the kinetics of the reactions¹⁴. In methanol the observed rate increases rapidly upto 40% (v/v) then increases slowly. Methanol shows about 1 : 1 association with water that does not change very much with concentration. It is reasonable to expect that the polar OH group of methanol hydrogen bonds with water, and that this type of association would be relatively constant until higher alcohol concentrations, where solute-solute interactions become important.

Aqueous ethanol has been termed as typically aqueous (TA) mixture⁴. A TA solvent exerts a water 'structure-forming' action, the solvent cospheres around each solute overlapping and mutually enhancing water-water interactions and therefore, the rate increases.

Dielectric constant : The dielectric constant of the medium plays a very important role. If the solvent effect is only a dielectric constant effect, then a graph of $\log k_{\psi}$ vs reciprocal of the dielectric constant (D) would yield a straight line. The plots of $\log k_{\psi}$ vs $1/D$ (Fig.

Fig. 1. Variation of pseudo-first order rate constant k_{ψ} with the mole fraction (X) of organic cosolvent in the base catalysed hydrolysis of PBHA

Fig. 2. Correlation of hydrolysis rates of PBHA with dielectric constant of the medium

2) in all the solvents were less satisfactory and showed a scattering of points, which could only be resolved into straight line by omitting certain points and considering limited solvent compositions.

The increase in the content of organic cosolvent results in a decrease of dielectric constant of the medium and an increase of the reaction rate. This may indicate that in the presence

TABLE 2—CALCULATED VALUES OF E_a , ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger IN DIFFERENT SOLVENT MIXTURES

Parameter	Solvent % (v/v)							
	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80
Dioxane :								
E_a	92.2	91.5	90.2	85.8	84.8	79.2	73.1	62.2
ΔH^\ddagger	89.4	89.1	88.1	83.6	81.8	76.1	70.3	60.9
ΔS^\ddagger	-57	-56	-56	-67	-68	-82	-97	-122
ΔG^\ddagger	106.4	105.6	104.7	103.4	101.9	100.4	98.9	97.1
DMSO :								
E_a	111	-	96.9	88.4	-	-	49.2	-
ΔH^\ddagger	108.3	-	94.2	86.7	-	-	45.9	-
ΔS^\ddagger	-2	-	-40	-60	-	-	-165	-
ΔG^\ddagger	105.8	-	106.1	104.4	-	-	95.0	-
MeOH :								
E_a	83.6	-	97.3	-	95.2	-	-	-
ΔH^\ddagger	81.4	-	95.3	-	93.0	-	-	-
ΔS^\ddagger	-81	-	-34	-	-39	-	-	-
ΔG^\ddagger	105.3	-	105.4	-	104.4	-	-	-
EtOH :								
E_a	85.3	-	90.9	-	98.3	-	-	-
ΔH^\ddagger	82.9	-	88.7	-	95.8	-	-	-
ΔS^\ddagger	-79	-	-53	-	-29	-	-	-
ΔG^\ddagger	106.3	-	104.3	-	104.3	-	-	-
Me ₂ CO :								
E_a	81.6	-	78.4	-	90.0	81.9	84.7	-
ΔH^\ddagger	78.9	-	76.1	-	87.3	79.4	81.9	-
ΔS^\ddagger	-91	-	-92	-	-51	-73	-63	-
ΔG^\ddagger	105.8	-	103.5	-	102.4	101.1	100.7	-
DMF :								
E_a	105	-	96.8	-	98.4	-	-	-
ΔH^\ddagger	102.9	-	93.9	-	95.7	-	-	-
ΔS^\ddagger	-15	-	-35	-	-25	-	-	-
ΔG^\ddagger	107.3	-	104.1	-	103.0	-	-	-
MeCN :								
E_a	108	-	100	-	95.3	-	89.4	-
ΔH^\ddagger	105.3	-	97.5	-	92.7	-	86.9	-
ΔS^\ddagger	-13	-	-32	-	-37	-	-46	-
ΔG^\ddagger	108.9	-	107.0	-	103.5	-	100.5	-

E_a , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger in kJ mol^{-1} ; ΔS^\ddagger $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$.

of organic cosolvent, solvation of the activated complex leading to the formation of intermediate is facilitated.

Activation parameters : The activation energy value (E_a) (Table 2) decreases with increasing percentage of dioxane, DMSO, MeCN and DMF. If the decrease is attributed to the solvation change, then one of the state (reactant or transition state) is more prone to solvation than the other. Since the transition state is a large dipolar anion with two units of negative charge in it, its solvation will increase with increasing

percentage of the solvents compared to the initial state. Naturally E_a value will decrease. Here, the activated complex is more solvated than the reactants, consequently the lowering of potential energy causes a decrease in energy of activation of the reaction, and the reaction rate is thus increased. While E_a shows no such trend in case of acetone, methanol and ethanol solvent medium.

The temperature dependence of the rate constants of the hydrolysis reaction was analysed by a least-squares procedure using a computer

program based on Eyring's equation, which produces values for ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger . The results (Table 2) show that the activation parameters are sensitive to solvent composition. Some useful insight as regards to the change in the structural aspects of the solvents might be obtained from the change in ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger , which contain important contributions. In dioxane, DMSO, MeCN and DMF, both the reduced enthalpy and entropy as predicted by the Hughes-Ingold theory, suggest the involvement of a more highly solvated transition state. Table 2 shows that the values of ΔS^\ddagger are negative in all solvent mixtures investigated. This implies that in all of these solvent mixtures the polar transition state is preferentially solvated by water molecules. Thus a reorganisation of solvent molecules occurs on going from the initial state to transition state. A decrease in ΔH^\ddagger value is observed, owing to relative stabilisation of the transition state. In all the cases ΔG^\ddagger increases slightly with increase in solvent content. The lesser dependence of ΔG^\ddagger is due largely to the general linear compensation between the enthalpy and entropy of activation at a given temperature.

Experimental

N-Phenylbenzohydroxamic acid was prepared by a standard method. Sodium hydroxide used was of A.R. grade. Dioxane (B.D.H., A.R.), acetone (Pfizer, certified reagent), DMSO, DMF and acetonitrile (all Merck, G.R.) were used as such. Ferric chloride solution used in the colorimetric procedure was prepared by dissolution of anhydrous ferric chloride (Reidel, A.R.) (10 g) in distilled water (1 lit) containing concentrated HCl (100 ml). The decrease of hydroxamic acid was followed spectrophotometrically using its reaction with Fe^{3+} . Solutions for rate measurements were prepared by adding a preweighed sample of PBHA in solvent to the appropriate temperature equilibrated basic solution. An aliquot (2 ml) of the reaction mixture was periodically removed and added to FeCl_3 solution (5 ml) and the resulting solution was diluted to 10

ml and its absorbance determined with an EC 5700 A spectrophotometer set at 520 nm. Beer's law was obeyed by the system. Pseudo-first order rate constants were obtained from the slope of the appropriate graph and by equation. Least-square analysis was carried out on a WIPRO 386 computer under MS-DOS.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. R. K. Misra, Head and Prof. S. G. Tandon, former Head, School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, for facilities.

References

1. C. REICHARDT, "Solvent and Solvent Effects in Organic Chemistry", 2nd. ed., VCH Verlagsgesellschaft mbH, Weinheim, 1988; E. BUNCEL and H. WILSON, *Adv. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1977, **14**, 133; E. S. AMIS, "Solvent Effects on Reaction Rates and Mechanisms", Academic, New York, 1966; E. M. ARNETT in "Physicochemical Process in Mixed Aqueous Solvents", ed. F. FRANKS, Heinemann, London, 1967; R. GOITEIN and T. C. BRUCE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, **76**, 432; C. D. RITCHIE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **105**, 3573, and references therein
2. A. J. PARKER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **69**, 1
3. H. M. ABU EL-NADER, M. N. H. MOUSSA and MOSTOFA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 868; R. C. JHA, A. K. GUPTA, R. KUMAR, B. SINGH and L. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **52**, 157
4. D. D. ROBERTS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 4037.
5. O. PYTELA, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1990, **55**, 634, 644; 1989, **54**, 136.
6. K. K. GHOSH and S. GHOSH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1994, **33**, 1369.
7. C. K. INGOLD, "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", Cornell University Press, Ithaca, 1953.
8. J. R. HOLMES, D. KIVELSON and W. C. DRINKARD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 4677; S. K. GARG and C. P. SMYTH, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, **43**, 2959.
9. M. J. BLANDMER and J. BURGESS, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1975, **4**, 55.
10. D. T. SAWYER and J. L. ROBERTS, JR., *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1988, **21**, 469.
11. P. ROHDEWALD and M. MOLDNER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 2710; C. DE VISSAR and G. SOMSEN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1974, **92**, 159; J. BOUGARD and R. JODOT, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1975, **7**, 1165.
12. R. A. ROBINSON and H. S. HARNED, *Chem. Rev.*, 1941, **28**, 419.
13. I. H. UM, G. LEE, H. YOON and D. S. KWON, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1992, **33**, 2023; I. H. UM, *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **11**, 173.
14. C. H. SPINK and J. C. WYCKOFF, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, **76**, 1660.

